

Agritourism: A Way Towards Upliftment of Indian Farmers

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Introduction

Agriculture is India's most important economic field. Agriculture employs about 65% of the workforce, either directly or indirectly. The agriculture sector accounts for about 13% of overall GDP. Adding new income-generating practises to current agriculture will undoubtedly boost agriculture's contribution to national GDP.

This will be accomplished by agritourism. In the Indian tourism industry, agritourism is the most recent concept. It allows you to have a genuine, enchanting, and honest encounter with real life. Agritourism promotion necessitates intellectual alignment with rural tourism, wellness tourism, and adventure tourism.

Agritourism Meaning

World Tourism Organization (1998) defines agritourism as “ involves accommodation being offered in the farmhouse or in a separate guesthouse, providing meals and organizing guests’ activities in the observation and participation in the farming operations.” Agritourism may include- outdoor recreation, educational experiences, entertainment (harvest festivals), hospitality services (farm stay, guided tour), on farm direct sales.

Rural tourism differs from agritourism in two ways: first, rural tourism businesses are not all located on farms or in agriculture plants, and second, they do not produce additional revenue for agriculture businesses.

A Diagrammatic representation of agritourism practices in India (Chatterjee et al., 2019)

Agritourism and its probable impacts in Indian consumers(Chatterjee et al., 2019)

Scope of Agri-Tourism

- 1. A low-cost gateway:** Agri-Tourism has the lowest costs of food, lodging, entertainment, and transport. The visitor base is widened as a result of this. Agri-Tourism is a term that brings travel and tourism to a wider audience, broadening the reach of tourism due to its cost-effectiveness.
- 2. Curiosity about the farming industry and lifestyle:** People with origins in villages have always been curious about food supplies, plants, livestock, raw materials such as wood, handicrafts, cultures, history, custom, dresses, and rural lifestyles. Agri-tourism, which circles around farmers, towns, and agriculture, has the ability to elicit the interest of this demographic.
- 3. Strong demand for wholesome family-oriented leisure events:** Villages provide recreational facilities to people of all ages, including children of all ages, adults of all ages, males and females, and the entire family at a lower rate. The entire family will enjoy a range of activities such as rural sports, markets, food, clothing, and nature.
- 4. The urban population's health consciousness and their need for solace in nature-friendly means:** Life has become more difficult as a result of modern lifestyles, and the overall lifespan has decreased. As a result, people are still looking for natural ways to make life more peaceful. Ayurveda, a natural medical approach, has its origins in villages. Villagers' traditional medical experience is valued.
- 5. The need for harmony and tranquillity:** Modern life is the product of a wide range of thoughts and practises. Every human strives to work harder in various ways in order to earn more money and enjoy modern conveniences. As a result, harmony is never in his system. Tourism is a way of looking for a peaceful place to visit. Agri-Tourism is founded on peace and tranquillity since it is located away from urban centres and close to nature.

Here are Some of the Agri-Tourist Destinations in India (Chatterjee et al., 2019)

North: R.O.S.E (Rural Opportunity for Social Elevation) works with the agri-tourism model in Uttarakhand's Bageshwar district, where visitors can stay in homestays amidst wheat fields and scenic mountain views and participate in daily work such as cooking, cultivating crops, constructing toilets, teaching English to school children, and other activities.

East: Zuluk or Dzuluk is a hamlet in East Sikkim on the Indo-China frontier. It is a relatively recent and offbeat tourist destination, strategically located at an altitude of about 3000 metres (10100 feet). Many visitors come to Zuluk to get a snapshot of the old Silk Route, and they have a range of homestays to choose from.

Central: In the central part of the region, there is a magnificent location known as Rawla Kaneriya, which is owned by the royal family of Jamnia. Agri-tourism at Rawla Kaneriya includes farm tours, farm holidays, farm bed and breakfast lodging, camping, nature research, cross-country skiing, picnics, hayrides, seminars, fishing, and other sports. The evening storytelling sessions contribute to the ethereal atmosphere.

South: The Andhra Pradesh Tourism Development Corporation (APTDC) has devised a novel concept of agri-tourism to promote rural tourism, which will feature integrated lush green horticulture farms, dairy, fishing, vegetable poly houses, and even guest houses for tourists to stay for a few days or longer and gain exposure to rural rustic life and natural environment, as well as rural eateries.

West: The indigenous homestays Shaam-e-Sarhad in Hodka, Gujarat's Kutch district, are close to the international border and have sparse vegetation. Yet, from November to March, when the atmosphere is pleasant and several festivals are held, the villagers, who are mainly shepherds, never hesitate to welcome visitors. Tourists have the choice of staying in mud huts or traditional cottages with western toilets, and can sample the local cuisine with gusto. The area has a long and illustrious tradition of art and craft, which is on display in the nearby artisan village. It also seeks to encourage new and creative approaches to collective action in rural communities in order to increase livelihood opportunities.

Opportunities for agritourism challenges and the intermittent network (Chatterjee et al., 2019).

Conclusion

Agritourism offers a rare opportunity to merge elements of the tourism and agriculture industries and provide visitors, farmers, and communities with a variety of commercial, educational, and social benefits. Agritourism provides farmers with an alternative source of revenue as well as a channel for direct marketing to customers. It boosts the tourism industry by increasing the number of tourists and the duration of their stay in a given region. Agritourism has the ability to expand municipal tax bases and provide new job prospects for residents. Agritourism also offers public educational resources, aids in the preservation of farm lands, and encourages states to establish commercial enterprises. While agritourism can open up new revenue streams for farmers and landowners, it also raises new legal concerns.

Agritourism can be a lucrative business. Farmers would have to put in a lot of effort and learn a lot of new skills. Agritourism events must be made aware of by visitor bureaus and chambers of commerce so that they can assist with their promotion. If all of the main players are active from the beginning, agritourism is a win-win scenario.

References

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